

LIFE PREDICTION ANALYSIS: DIRECTIONS AND DIVAGATIONS

Kenneth L. Reifsnider
Reynolds Metals Professor of
Engineering Science and Mechanics
Materials Response Group
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg, Virginia 24061-4899 USA

ABSTRACT

Life prediction as an engineering enterprise is a recent phenomenon. The technical definition of associated problems in physics and mechanics is still being sought, and rigor is more often added as an applique than woven into a philosophical fabric of understanding of long-term behavior. Nevertheless, life prediction is one of three basic questions before the engineering community: "How strong is it?" "How stiff is it?" "How long will it last?" The answers to these questions control the performance of all engineering structures.

The present paper will address the questions of definition of problems, interpretation of physical behavior, development of rational philosophy, and construction of engineering models associated with life prediction. Particular attention will be given to the identification of coherent directions for continued work and divagations that do not appear to be part of a general approach to the subject.

LIFE PREDICTION--THE PROBLEM

Life prediction is a practical problem motivated by the need to have materials serve an engineering purpose over some period of time or under some prescribed set of circumstances. In general, the service behavior of a component is controlled by stiffness, strength, and life. The deflections and dynamic behavior are controlled by stiffness; the load carrying capability and resistance to damage is controlled by strength; and the reliability, safety, and life cycle cost of a component is defined by the life of the member. At the material level, stiffness is generally defined as a property, which has specific values for a specific material in a given condition. Strength is less commonly thought of as a property, since it is sometimes more sensitive to the details of the internal structure of a material than is stiffness. However, the investigation and use of composite materials has provided us with numerous practical examples of materials in which the stiffness is at least as sensitive to

the details of internal structure as is the strength, and has provided us with a few examples of materials in which the stiffness is changed by a change in internal structure while the strength remains essentially unchanged [1]. Hence, while we need to be very careful about the definition of stiffness and strength, and meticulous in our control of the manner in which they are measured, stiffness and strength of materials should be regarded as properties, to be used in constitutive equations common to mechanics representations.

However, such an argument cannot be made for life. Life is not an independent property uniquely defined by a material, even if the conditions of the material and the conditions under which life is measured are carefully controlled and described. Life is defined by a process and a criterion, as suggested in Fig. 1. The process consists of the development of a state of stress and state of material which changes over the life of the component. At any given point in time, the stress state is defined by the loading history, geometry, and properties of the material involved, combined with information regarding the manner in which internal structure is altered during the response of the material up to that point of life. The material state is defined by the properties and deformation history of the material or material elements involved, and by the damage state which has been created by various damage events associated with the response of the material up to that point. The damage state may include events associated with mechanical response such as micro-cracking, but may also include degradation associated with thermal effects, chemical effects, kinetics, or other thermodynamic processes. Properties may include stiffness, strength, conductivity, mechanical damping characteristics, and other constitutive characterizations. Internal structure changes are associated with the damage state and include changes in the basic nature of the inhomogeneity, anisotropy, and (geometry of the) constituent materials and boundaries (including free surfaces).

The criterion used to define life is established by combining limits on the remaining strength, remaining stiffness, allowable property degradation, or other structural performance requirements with a philosophy which relates the current state of stress and state of material to those limits, as suggested by Fig. 2. Examples of such criteria include yield or failure "theories" such as the Tsai-Hill or Von Mises criteria, limits on the characteristic frequencies of vibration of a structure, various reliability criteria, etc. Figure 2 emphasizes that philosophy is involved in such a criterion, in the sense that considerable understanding and perception is involved in the manner in which the state of stress and state of material is related to the performance that is sought. These response or performance criteria are not physical laws. They are phenomenological characterizations which are constructed as representations of physical observations. They are limited in their validity by the accuracy of the observations, the generality of the observations, and the generality of the understandings used to extend those observations to unfamiliar circumstances.

Life prediction as an engineering enterprise is somewhat of a dichotomy. It is rarely taught as a disciplinary subject in university classrooms, and is usually relegated to the final steps in a design process. Yet, the safety, reliability, and durability of materials plays an unparalleled role in the selection of materials, the manner in which

materials are used, and the economy with which materials function in engineering components. Safety-critical structures such as aircraft cannot be certified for service without an approved methodology for predicting the lifetime of such a structure. And the acceptability of entire classes of materials (such as ceramics) by the engineering community for use in structures and components often hinges on our ability to predict the life of those components. While statistical considerations of behavior and phenomenological/empirical descriptions of observations are useful for these purposes, they are not substitutes for understandings of the physics, mechanics, and chemistry of the associated events. We cannot reliably avoid anything we cannot reliably predict. Therefore, if we are to avoid precipitous or even disastrous failures reliably, we must develop rigorous and rational life prediction methods based on firm understandings and sound philosophy.

The objective of the present paper is to bring together some of the salient aspects of this problem and to discuss current approaches which the author believes are valid and appropriate candidates for exploitation. Some attempt will also be made to identify spurious approaches (defined within the context of the author's prejudices). The presentation approach to be used is illustrated in Fig. 3. The description will be based on the concept of a "process," since it is believed that that concept is most critical and least well understood among those associated with the general topic. The discussion will be further subdivided into three categories, dealing with initiation, growth, and interaction events, since it is believed that the physical characteristics and consequences, and the analytical descriptions of those three categories are relatively distinct. The paper will conclude with a general modeling representation peculiar to the author's experience and current activity.

INITIATION

Figure 4 is a generalization of a familiar concept used to discuss the life of materials and components. The ordinate of the diagram is the "level of influence" which may be the amplitude or range of applied cyclic stress, the level of temperature, the level of moisture (or moisture gradient), the chemical concentration or concentration gradient, or any other external influence that produces changes in material properties or response which ultimately define how long the element lasts. The abscissa indicates the period of response, which may be measured by the number of cycles of loading, by sidereal time, or by any convenient interpreted variable. Life is indicated by the locus of points which relates the level of influence to the period of response. The "process" that we have been discussing in Figs. 1 and 3 results in a reduction of properties or capability to respond to the applied influence as suggested by the schematic curve beginning at point C and ending at point B in Fig. 4. Curve C-B in Fig. 4 is actually a plot of the value of the "criterion" discussed in Fig. 2. When the criterion for the end of life is reduced to the level of influence, life is defined.

We shall call the events which are associated with the reduction of properties or response "damage" as a collective term, albeit an imprecise one. Hence, we are left with the argument that materials (and engineering components) have finite life because of a process of events which

initiate, grow, and interact to cause reductions in properties or response. We are concerned in this section with initiation.

Figure 5 suggests several types of common events which initiate in engineering materials. In some cases, the life of materials can be discussed and described in terms of the initiation of those events. The first of the categories is micro-surface formation. This is almost an entirely geometric event. It may consist of micro-cracking of single phases, separation of interfacial boundaries between constituent phases, crack formation between the plies of laminated materials, etc. For particulate composites, these cracks may initiate at the boundaries of the particulate reinforcements [2]. For laminated composites with continuous fiber reinforcements, matrix cracks typically initiate through the thickness of individual plies and increase in density under sustained or cyclic loading until a "characteristic damage state for matrix cracking" is reached [3-4]. One can consider the initiation of these events in terms of a driving force and a corresponding material resistance. For geometric discontinuities such as micro-surface formation, one approach to this concept is provided by the subdiscipline of linear elastic fracture mechanics. That treatment is based on the definition of a boundary value problem which represents the singular stress field associated with the tip of a crack in a continuous body, as indicated in Fig. 6. The resulting stress fields have the general form shown in Eqn. (1).

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{K}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} f_{ij}(\theta) \quad (1)$$

in which the field stress intensity is represented by K , and the spatial distribution as a function of the angle θ (shown in Fig. 6) is given by the function $f_{ij}(\theta)$. The functional form of the field stress intensity, K , is shown in Eqn. (2), in which g is a function of the geometry and the nature of the remote loading.

$$K = \sigma g \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (2)$$

The singular stress field is highly localized and is "anchored" to the tip of the crack. The order of the singularity in Eqn. (1) may be somewhat different if plastic deformation near the crack tip is accounted for [6] or in special situations involving interfaces between anisotropic materials [7]. The state of stress for this type of geometric defect retains the same general nature as that indicated in Eqn. (1).

In order to relate this state of stress to the state of the material associated with micro-surface formation, one usually assumes that all engineering materials contain "initial flaws" which may be discontinuities in the materials themselves or flaws introduced by the manufacturing or joining process. The "driving force" for the initiation of a micro-crack of engineering consequence from such a flaw can be characterized by the field stress intensity given in Eqn. (2). The "state of the material" to be compared to that "state of stress" is commonly characterized by a parameter called the "material toughness" or the "critical field stress intensity," K_C . Hence, the "criterion" in Fig. 1 is a single parameter criterion which states that cracking will initiate when the value of the field stress intensity exceeds the critical value.

4.5

An alternative representation is based on a concept introduced by Griffith who argued that the formation of a crack was driven by the stored elastic energy released by the relaxation of stresses in a volume of material around the crack. Equation (3) is the relationship used to represent that energy release provided by Griffith, in which σ is the remote stress, a is the half-crack length, and E is the elastic modulus of the material.

$$U = \frac{\pi \sigma^2 a^2}{E} \quad (3)$$

Crack formation is resisted by an elastic surface energy per unit area, γ_e . The condition for crack formation can be found by determining the extremum of the total energy of the system resulting in expression (4).

$$\frac{\pi \sigma^2 a}{E} = 2\gamma_e \quad (4)$$

U = decrease in the elastic energy caused by introducing the crack
 γ_e = elastic surface energy per unit area
 a^e = half-length of through-crack

The quality on the left hand side of that expression is the "strain energy release rate", G , which characterizes the state of stress, and the right hand side of Eqn. (4) can be thought of as the material resistance to crack extension or formation, which characterizes the state of the material. Again, the "criterion" that compares these two states is generally a single parameter concept which compares the strain energy release rate to a critical value of that quantity, G_c . However, if crack initiation (or extension) is driven by several modes of deformation such as crack opening (mode 1), sliding of the crack faces perpendicular to the direction of the crack front (mode 2), or sliding of the crack faces parallel to the crack front (Mode 3), so that driving forces G_I , G_{II} , and G_{III} are available, the "philosophy" in Fig. 2 which relates these driving forces collectively to crack initiation or extension is not so simple as the comparison of a single parameter (c.f. [9]).

It is apparent that the criterion for micro-crack formation may not be the criterion which defines life of a material or a component. Cracks may initiate at the micro-level and grow in an unstable fashion over a short distance until the internal stress state changes, the crack is diverted by a boundary of some type, or other circumstances terminate its growth. Under those conditions, the micro-crack initiation sequence defines a damage accumulation process which controls the life of the component in a more collective fashion. More will be said of this in our subsequent discussion.

The second category of damage initiation in Fig. 5 is anelastic deformation. In the present context, we will choose creep deformation as an example of this category for our discussion purposes. Some of the philosophy appropriate for this discussion also applies to physical situations where life is defined by chemical degradation or by other physical "reaction rates." The Arrhenius equation shown below is the conceptual basis for modern chemical reaction rate theory and has also spawned a popular approach to the creep life problem. Based on the

argument that creep deformation is generally caused by activation processes such as thermally activated plastic deformation or various diffusion processes, a life equation having the general form shown in relationship (6) is commonly postulated.

$$\text{Rate} = \hat{A} \exp \left[- \frac{\hat{B}}{T} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Life} = A \exp \left[\frac{\epsilon}{kT} \right] ; \epsilon_0 = \epsilon_a - \epsilon(\sigma) \quad (6)$$

In that equation, the time to failure (called "life") is thought to be proportional to the exponent of the energy available to drive the phenomenon, ϵ , divided by Plank's constant and the absolute temperature, T . As suggested by the equation, the available energy, ϵ , can be thought of as the activation energy or activation "barrier" associated with the phenomenon. As suggested in Eqn. (6), ϵ may have the general form of the difference between the absolute activation energy, ϵ_0 , and the energy available from the applied influences, ϵ_a . If A in Eqn. (6) is an absolute material constant, and ϵ depends on stress alone, the familiar time-temperature relationship postulated by Larson and Miller, shown in Eqn. (7) is obtained, where C is a material constant, and $f(\sigma)$ is a function of stress alone.

$$T (\log t + C) = f(\sigma) \quad (7)$$

From the standpoint of the organization of our subject suggested in Fig. 1, the "process" described by Eqns. (5-7) consists of an activation phenomenon, and the "criterion" is engineering failure defined either by rupture or by an allowable deformation under constant conditions. For viscoelastic deformation processes, this approach is well developed [10,11].

Another physical manner in which damage initiation can determine life is through damage accumulation. In such circumstances, micro events such as crack formation, void development, or various other pointwise events nucleate in large numbers under sustained loading or constant amplitude cyclic loading [2], [12], and [13]. In 1958, Kachanov introduced the concept of "continuity," D , of a material, defined in the sense that damage accumulation changes the proportion of material available to carry an applied load. If damage reduces the available cross section to A_t as shown in Eqn. (8) below,

$$A_t = A_0(1-D) \quad (8)$$

the stress σ_t at a given time, t , can be given by

$$\sigma_t = \frac{\sigma}{(1-D)} \quad (9)$$

Kachanov and subsequent authors have discussed various forms for the "evolution" of the damage parameter or the "continuity" as he called it. For the tertiary creep of ductile materials, the form shown in Eqn. (10) is common [14].

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = \left[\frac{|\sigma|}{C(1-D)} \right]^r (1-D)^{-q} \quad (10)$$

The material constants, r , q , and C are obtained from creep tests conducted under various conditions, and from the constraints on D such that $D=0$ when the test begins, and $D=1$ at rupture. In terms of the time to rupture, t_c , the damage parameter D may have the form of Eqn. (11) for creep deformation of ductile materials.

$$D = 1 - \left[1 - \frac{t}{t_c} \right]^{\frac{1}{r+q+1}} \quad (11)$$

For cyclic plastic deformation, Eqn. (9) may take the form

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma}{(1-D)} = K \Delta\epsilon_p^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (12)$$

in which K and M are material characteristics under plastic conditions which relate the stress range $\Delta\sigma$ to the strain range $\Delta\epsilon_p$. In that case, Douglas and Plumtree give the continuity factor as

$$D = 1 - \left(\frac{\Delta\epsilon^*}{\Delta\epsilon_p} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (13)$$

in which $\Delta\epsilon^*$ is the strain range at steady state or stabilized conditions. The corresponding evolution equation may have the form

$$\frac{\delta D}{\delta N} = \left[\frac{K}{2B} \right]^{\beta} \Delta\epsilon_p^{B/m} [1-D]^{-p} \quad (14)$$

in which B , β , and p are temperature dependent material characteristics which may be obtained from the relation of cyclic plastic behavior coupled with damage. Using the common constraints on D , Eqn. (14) may be integrated to estimate the life in number of cycles, N_F , as

$$N_F = \frac{1}{[p+1] \left[\frac{K}{2B} \right]^{\beta} \Delta\epsilon_p^{B/m}} \quad (15)$$

The constants in Eqn. (15) are obtained from the results of fatigue tests and cyclic stress-strain tests which provide the damage parameter D as a function of the instantaneous stiffness according to Eqn. (12).

The Kachanov damage parameter concept has been rather widely adopted and forms the basis of what is popularly called the "damage mechanics" approach to life prediction. A special effort has been made to apply this idea to high temperature creep deformation and creep rupture where it is extremely difficult to follow or analytically model the specific details of the various physical phenomena which contribute to the fracture event. Complex combinations of micro-fracture, diffusion, and anelastic deformation typically contribute to that phenomenon. Rather than deal with the individual details of these events, one can generalize the concept of the damage parameter to represent the collective consequences of these micro-details and their interactions.

This general idea is the basis of continuum approaches to damage description and life prediction. Several important fundamental features of such an approach greatly influence their utility. When a damage parameter such as the "continuity" introduced by Kachanov is used to characterize a large body of internal events, the details of those events are inevitably lost, or smoothed, or averaged in some fashion. This is logical and useful in the same sense that continuum mechanics averages response of submicroscopic quantities such as atomic motions and molecular details which are not of fundamental or specific interest to engineering response (in most cases). However, for composite materials, the geometric scale at which response is averaged into a damage parameter is an essential consideration. Indeed, we must make specific choices for specific circumstances to insure that our analytical modeling is sufficiently general to avoid having paradgms obscured by tedia, and sufficiently specific to insure that the micro- or submicro-details that control the physical phenomenon we are attempting to describe are not lost in the generality of our description. Of particular concern is the loss of information concerning internal geometry. If one uses a generalized parameter to describe internal cracking in a composite material, for example, differences in the internal geometry of micro-cracks associated with different constituent sizes or different constituent properties (anisotropy and inhomogeneity) may cause dramatically different damage and failure modes which can never be anticipated by a continuum model not sensitive to those details.

A more generalized approach to the continuum representation of damage is provided by introducing damage vectors or tensors as internal thermodynamic variables. This generalization has some important features which are pertinent to our present discussion. It is not hard to imagine that a single scalar parameter such as the "continuity" introduced by Kachanov may not be sufficient to describe complex damage states, especially in composite materials. Tensor representations (of various orders) have been introduced by a variety of authors (c.f., [15-18]). A common application of this approach is the representation of patterned arrays of transverse cracks prior to localization [15]. For the purpose of our discussion, we consider the example provided by Weitsman [16].

He represents the internal free energy (say, the Gibbs' free energy) as

$$\Phi = \hat{\Phi} (\sigma_{ij}, m, T, d_{[ij]}) \quad (16)$$

and

$$\epsilon_{ij} = - \frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta \sigma_{ij}} \quad ; \quad \hat{\mu} = \frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta m} \quad ; \quad R_{[ij]} = \frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta d_{[ij]}} \quad (17)$$

in which ϵ_{ij} are infinitesimal strains, σ_{ij} are components of the Cauchy stress, $R_{[ij]}$ are the "affinities" to the unsymmetric damage tensor $d_{[ij]}$, μ is the chemical potential, and T is temperature. Using fundamental principles, Weitsman then obtains the evolution equation

$$\dot{\psi}_{[ij]} = \dot{d}_{[ij]} = \hat{\psi}_{[ij]} (\sigma_{ij}, d_{[pq]}, Z_d, m) \quad (18)$$

in which z_l is the gradient of the chemical potential, and m is the moisture content, and the constitutive relation

$$f_k = \hat{f}_k (\sigma_{ij}, d_{[pq]}, Z_l, m) \quad (19)$$

in which f_k are the components of the moisture-flux vector. Equation (18) must reflect the isotropy or anisotropy of the initial undamaged material. If it is assumed that the infinitesimal strains and stresses are small, the functions in (16), (18), and (19) may be expanded in a Taylor series in stress and truncated at an appropriate power. Then if the chemical potential μ varies only in the x_1 direction, whereby

$$Z_1 = \frac{\hat{\delta}\mu}{\delta x_1}, \quad Z_2 = Z_3 = 0 \quad (20)$$

and no cracks cut across fibers (whereby $d_{[1,2]}=0$), Weitsman obtains

$$\dot{d}_{[31]} = (r + RZ_1^2) d_{[31]} \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{d}_{[32]} = (r - RZ_1^2) d_{[32]} \quad (22)$$

$$\hat{\mu} = X_0 + [X_1 + X_2 (d_{[31]}^2 - d_{[32]}^2)] \sigma_0 \quad (23)$$

$$f_1 = D \frac{\delta m}{\delta x_1} + \hat{D} \frac{\delta (d_{[31]}^2 - d_{[32]}^2)}{\delta x_1} \quad (24)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} r, R, \hat{D} \text{ and } D \text{ can be shown to depend at most on } m, \\ \sigma_0, Z_1^2, \sigma_0 Z_1^2, (d_{[31]}^2 + d_{[32]}^2), \sigma_0 (d_{[31]}^2 - d_{[32]}^2) \text{ and} \\ Z_1^2 (d_{[31]}^2 - d_{[32]}^2) \text{ while } X_0, X_1 \text{ and } X_2 \\ \text{depend at most on only } m \text{ and } (d_{[31]}^2 + d_{[32]}^2) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Several aspects of those relationships are important to our present discussion. First, the damage model suggests that damage growth levels tend to vary nonlinearly with stress. Second, Eqn. (24) suggests that in the presence of damage, moisture flux is related to moisture gradients through a stress and damage-affected diffusivity D . In fact, the parameter D represents a coupling between moisture flux and damage gradients. Weitsman uses this association to explain the trend towards

damage localization due to moisture ingress.

In the present context this treatment serves to remind us that inherently time-dependent phenomena such as moisture diffusion and chemical activity may be quite naturally related to damage development events such as micro-cracking in the physical world, despite a rather pervasive tendency for us to separate them in our modeling representations. Returning to Figs. 1 and 5, continuum representations such as the example given above have considerable potential for the description of damage initiation and accumulation as the "process" suggested by Fig. 1 and can be combined with a criterion of some type to predict life under very complex circumstances in which damage modes interact, and failure may be precipitated by a combination of physical phenomena.

Before leaving the "initiation" category of our consideration of processes, we mention one other continuum approach to life prediction which depends upon a specific account of localized behavior. This approach is usually associated with low cycle fatigue and is commonly called the "local strain approach" [20-23]. For present purposes, we are interested only in the following features of that approach. Phenomenological representations of the number of cycles to failure, N_f , typically have the form shown in Eqn. (26),

$$2N_f = \left(\frac{\Delta \epsilon_p}{2\epsilon_f^c} \right)^{1/c} \quad (26)$$

in which $\Delta \epsilon_p$ is the plastic strain range, ϵ_f^c is the fatigue ductility coefficient p and is frequently approximated by the true fracture ductility ϵ_f , and c is a material constant sometimes assumed to be a universal constant. The cyclic stress-strain response of such a material may fit a relationship such as that shown in Eqn. (27)

$$\Delta \epsilon_t = \frac{\Delta \sigma}{E} + m \left(\frac{\Delta \sigma}{G} \right)^{Z/\delta} \quad (27)$$

in which $\Delta \epsilon_t$ is the total strain range; $\Delta \sigma$ is the applied stress range; m , Z , γ , and G are material constants determined from experimental data. For nonuniform stress states such as those which appear near stress concentrations such as notches or cut-outs, an elastic-plastic stress concentration concept such as that described by Neuber [25]

$$K_\epsilon K_\sigma = K_t^2 \quad (28)$$

where K is the strain concentration factor, K_σ is the stress concentration factor, and K_t is the theoretical elastic stress concentration factor, can be used to relate the remote applied cyclic stress to the local strain behavior as suggested by Fig. 7. What is important to our present discussion is that these relationships can be established on a cycle-by-cycle basis. Hence, a spectrum of loading as shown in Fig. 7c can be interpreted in terms of the local strain response shown in Fig. 7e. Each of the closed stress-strain hysteresis loops in

Fig. 7e are then entered into an equation such as (26) to estimate the total life. The details of this process are complex but conceptually straightforward and can be found in numerous references including [20-25]. This specific account of local behavior is unique among life prediction techniques. It is also an extreme technique in the sense that a cycle-by-cycle approach could be very demanding analytically for more general circumstances. However, this method has become the dominant approach to low cycle fatigue life prediction in ductile materials, and has the advantage of including a specific account of inelastic material behavior.

DAMAGE GROWTH

The second major type of "process" which can control life, as noted in Fig. 3, is damage growth. This is a familiar category, since life determinations in homogeneous materials are generally dominated by single through-crack propagation. Earlier we discussed a condition for crack growth postulated by Griffith, and introduced the expression shown in Eqn. (3). That expression actually describes the energy balance at incipient propagation of a crack in terms of a material fracture toughness, G_c . Hence, Eqn. (3) can be written as Eqn. (29).

$$G(\sigma, \sigma) = G_c \quad (29)$$

While this equation may describe when a crack will begin to grow, it does not describe the rate of crack growth or the life of a component under prescribed conditions. Moreover, G_c may be a local mode-dependent directionally variable material property which depends on the local condition of the material, especially on the presence of inelastic deformation [27,28]. The material fracture toughness which may be appropriate for the prediction of the onset of delamination may not describe the material resistance to crack propagation after delamination has begun [29]. Indeed, this is a familiar situation for homogeneous metals in which fatigue crack propagation may occur at remote load levels which are less than half of those required to cause the onset of crack growth under quasi-static loading.

In the absence of better fundamental information, more complete understandings, and better analytical descriptions of the physical processes which control damage growth rates, empirical relationships have proliferated. It is common to postulate a relationship such as the Paris expression given in Eqn. (30),

$$\frac{da}{dn} = \bar{C} (\Delta K)^m \quad (30)$$

in which the change in crack length, a , with the number of cycles of applied loading, n , is proportional to the cyclic amplitude of the field stress intensity, ΔK , and \bar{C} and m are assumed to be material constants [30]. If the variation in the field stress intensity is given by a geometric factor, Y , times the change in remote applied stress, $\Delta \sigma$, and the half-crack length (or crack length for an edge crack) a according to the relationship

$$\Delta K = Y \Delta \sigma_a a^{1/2} \quad (31)$$

then time-to-failure relationships such as Eqn. (32) are obtained if the cyclic stress amplitude is constant throughout the loading.

$$t_f = \frac{\hat{C} [K_c^{2-m} - K_i^{2-m}]}{(2-m) \bar{C} Y^2 (\Delta \sigma_a)^2} \quad (32)$$

where K_c is the material toughness, K_i is the initial value of the field stress intensity, and c is a constant. If the ratio of the cyclic minimum to maximum stress, R , is included in the expression for crack growth rate (and if it remains constant throughout the test) expressions such as (33) (known as the Forman relationship) and (34) (known as the Walker relation) are obtained [31].

$$\frac{da}{dn} = \frac{C(\Delta K)^m}{(1-R) K_c - \Delta K} \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{da}{dn} = C \left(\frac{\Delta K}{(1-R)^{1-s}} \right)^m \quad (34)$$

where C , m , and s are material constants. If localized plasticity or other nonlinear behavior has a significant influence on the propagation of the crack, it may be necessary to replace the variation in field stress intensity with the variation in an appropriate path independent integral as suggested by Dowling and others [32,33]. Localized nonreversible deformation can also greatly influence the effective local stress field, reducing it by crack closure whereby residual stresses prevent a crack from opening in direct proportion to cyclic variations in the applied loading [34].

For fiber reinforced composite materials wherein the elastic modulus of the matrix is similar to that of the fibers and the interface between the two materials is poor, crack propagation may be significantly influenced by fiber bridging across the crack faces as the front of the crack runs ahead of the fiber fracture zones. The physical consequences of this phenomenon have been introduced into fracture mechanics characterizations of that propagation by means of "pseudo-closure forces" which act on the crack faces [35]. Fracture mechanics has also been applied successfully to the description of the initiation of crack growth perpendicular to the fibers in graphite epoxy systems [36]. However, there has been very little effort to predict life for that type of propagation mode, partly because crack propagation most commonly travels in directions parallel to the constituent material boundaries in composite systems if not along the interfaces between those constituents.

In summary, for most composite material systems, damage propagation plays a controlling role in the determination of life through delamination and debonding. In certain particulate reinforced systems and other

composite materials wherein the internal inhomogeneity does not play a major role in the micro-response, self-similar crack propagation in the sense normally identified with homogeneous materials may occur. In both cases, elastic or elastic-plastic fracture mechanics can be used to characterize the state of stress near the crack front. The state of the material (c.f. Fig. 3) is generally characterized by a toughness parameter, and life is determined from an empirical damage growth relationship estimated from curve fitting of laboratory data. While this procedure still suffers from a great many unsettled issues such as the unknown influences of multi-dimensional stress, physical explanations for the existence of thresholds below which propagation does not occur, the influence of various environmental effects such as temperature and aggressive chemical environments, the influence of inelastic deformation on variable amplitude response, the effect of frequency of loading (rate effects), and the influence of internal residual stresses in highly anisotropic and inhomogeneous materials, life prediction by damage propagation equations is the most widely practiced and most familiar method presently in use.

PROCESSES WHICH INVOLVE INTERACTION

In Fig. 1, we advanced an engineering definition of life based on a "process" and a "criterion." In Fig. 3 we further divided the idea of a process into three categories: initiation, growth, and interaction. Of course, these three categories may simply be different chronological stages in a damage process. Typical life prediction methods such as those discussed above assume that either initiation or damage growth dominates the damage process. The interaction of damage is not commonly considered. For composite materials, this may be a serious oversight. Composites are, by definition, inhomogeneous and are frequently anisotropic. Largely because of these characteristics, damage development in these materials is frequently complex, various, and cumulative. Multiple matrix crack formation in constituent phases as well as between phases, boundary decohesion between constituents or between plies in laminates, inelastic deformation, and chemical degradation may occur in a myriad of combinations of damage types and extents. While the inhomogeneity of these materials tends to isolate the growth of such defects, it does not prevent the interaction of the micro-stress fields associated with those events.

A typical example of this is provided by matrix crack formation in angle-ply laminated continuous-fiber reinforced materials such as typical engineering laminates of graphite epoxy. When matrix cracks form parallel to the fibers in adjacent plies which have differing orientations, the matrix cracks (which stop at the ply boundaries) may intersect at a point on the boundary to form a "crossed-crack" defect. This problem has been thoroughly discussed by Highsmith [37]. He found that the local stress field near the intersection of the two cracks was synergistic in the sense that it was not a simple superposition of the stress fields of the two individual cracks. For example, as shown in Fig. 8, the interlaminar normal stress which occurs at the point of interaction is significantly enhanced. Some of the physical consequences of this interaction of the stress field of the two cracks are easy to identify. Figure 9 shows an X-ray radiograph of matrix cracks in the 0 and 90° plies of a $[0/90_2]_s$ graphite epoxy specimen after about two-thirds of its lifetime has been expended under cyclic tension-tension loading. There are several "gray

regions" near the intersection of matrix cracks, which have been determined to be internal delaminations which form at the interface between the two plies in which the matrix cracks which cross are located. The fact that these internal delaminations are localized at the crack intersections suggests that the interaction of the stresses from the two cracks at that point is responsible for the development of that damage mode [38]. The interaction between localized delaminations and matrix cracks is even more significant and pronounced near the edge of a laminate [27,39].

A more general statement of the consequences of the interaction of stress fields associated with different types of damage is provided by the concept of "localization." The elevated stress field in the region of a damage event may cause that damage to grow in a self-similar fashion, or cause damage of a different type to initiate, or interact with stress fields caused by other damage events of a similar or dissimilar type. However, because of these locally elevated stress fields and because of the interaction between these stress fields, further damage is more likely to occur in these regions than in other regions in which there are no damage events. Hence, the more damage that occurs in a region, the more likely it is that further damage will occur in that region, which redoubles the chance that additional damage will occur, etc. This localization tendency is widely noted and discussed (c.f. [37,40]).

The interaction of damage events greatly complicates efforts to model this phenomenon analytically. While it is certainly possible to determine the stress fields associated with multiple cracks (or crack arrays), and "brute force" methods of accounting for all of the interactions of all of the defects associated with complex damage accumulation is theoretically possible in this age of super computers, it is difficult to estimate or even comprehend the amount of computational effort required to achieve meaningful descriptions of all of the associated micro-details of the stress fields associated with a given damage state, let alone a damage process. At the other extreme, attempting to average out the influence of all of the complex damage events into a "pseudo-continuum" having "pseudo-constitutive properties" results in the loss of critical information, especially regarding the geometry of micro-defects which frequently controls the consequences of damage accumulation, especially strength. Moreover, most of the continuum treatments that are used for "damage mechanics" are analytical formulations based on "dilute solution" assumptions which ignore interactions of any kind.

The author has proposed an approach to this situation based on a representative volume concept. Man-made composite materials generally have intentional inhomogeneity. Constituent materials chosen because of their desirable properties or characteristics are combined in a manner that best compensates for their shortcomings. The act of combination usually amounts to a mechanical arrangement of constituent phases. In order to optimize the consequent response and to insure some uniformity of composite properties on a spatial basis, this arrangement is usually a regular pattern such as the alignment and positioning of fibers in a continuous-fiber reinforced material or the regular distribution of particles in a particulate composite. (Two exceptions to this generality are randomly oriented short fiber composite materials in which the fiber volume fraction may vary substantially from point to point, resulting in somewhat degraded mechanical properties, and materials in which the

reinforcement volume fraction is intentionally varied to compensate for known variations in loading such as local reinforcements around load introduction regions.) These patterns of reinforcement create a specific pattern in the nucleation of damage events. Moreover, the interaction of the local stress fields around damage events such as matrix cracking in fibrous laminated composite materials can also create regular arrays of damage which forms a pattern that is "stable" or "saturated" for some range of loading conditions [3,41,1,42]. These regular patterns have been called "characteristic damage states" [3]. If such a generic pattern can be identified, it is possible to choose a "representative volume" of material which is similar to all other such volumes of material in a damage state in the continuum sense. Figure 10 illustrates that concept. Figure 11 provides a specific example of a representative volume for a fiber reinforced composite laminate in which matrix cracking forms a characteristic damage state, secondary cracking forms crossed-cracks, and fibers fail in the high-stress region of the localized damage.

The author has suggested that this representative volume be further divided into critical and subcritical elements. This division is based upon specific information concerning the failure mode and an understanding of the failure process for each such failure mode. A flow diagram of the manner in which this choice is made and used is shown in Fig. 12. The local geometric details associated with damage development prior to the final fracture event which are critical to the determination of the local stress field that causes final fracture are explicitly considered in a micro-mechanical treatment of the "subcritical elements" in the representative volume. Other details not important to the determination of the local stress field associated with the final failure event are grouped into continuum (phenomenological) representations of the "critical elements" in the representative volume, which are critical in the sense that the failure of those elements defines the failure of the representative volume and the global component. As suggested by Fig. 12, the critical elements are used to determine and specify the "state of the material" and the subcritical elements are used to determine and specify the "state of stress" which are combined (in a suitable failure criterion) to define the strength of the component. Damage growth and interaction is accounted for in the micro-mechanics representations of the subcritical elements, and degradation such as chemical attack or other events which occur on a scale which is finer than the "resolution" necessary to describe the mechanics and physics of the situation are accounted for by continuum constitutive representations of the behavior of the critical elements.

For such an approach, the reduction in strength can be calculated using an integral formulation suggested by the author, illustrated in Fig. 13 [43]. The quantities in that equation are evaluated in the critical element. The stresses that enter into the failure function are the stresses in the critical element calculated on the basis of the local geometry created by fracture in the subcritical elements, and the applied loading. The phenomenological information that goes into the strength or life constitutive equations that are used in the integral equation are characterizations of the material in the critical element (in the virgin or degraded condition).

The critical element concept has been applied to the prediction of the life of notched and unnotched composite laminate coupons under

tension, compression, and combined tension-compression loading with constant or variable cyclic amplitudes [44,45]. Since the residual strength equation in Fig. 13 is integrated incrementally, load sequence effects are predicted without the addition of "special features" to the model. Figure 14 shows an example of such sequence effects for block loading of a graphite epoxy laminate. The predicted life for a sequence of "block 1" loading for 100 thousand cycles followed by "block 2" loading to failure is about 17% longer than that predicted for the reverse sequence. Observations showed about a 23% difference [44].

Some efforts have been made (and are currently underway) to include various other factors in the critical element approach. Statistical considerations and time-dependent effects have been considered [46]. The constitutive information in the critical element enters the residual strength equation in Fig. 14 in the form of normalizing factors. The failure function may involve strength quantities such as X_1 , X_2 , and S in a failure criterion such as the Tsai-Hill equation shown below.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{X_2}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{X_1^2} + \left(\frac{\tau}{S}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (35)$$

The generalized time quantity is equal to the variable which is used to measure life; it may be equal to current sidereal time divided by the time to failure, or equal to current number of cycles divided by the life of the critical element under current conditions given by a phenomenological equation as suggested by the relationships below.

$$\tau = \frac{t}{t_f} ; \quad \frac{n}{N} \quad (36)$$

The time to failure, t_f , may be given by a rheological (kinetic) relationship such as Eqn. (37)

$$t_f = \alpha \int_1^{\hat{\sigma}} \frac{1/\hat{\sigma}^2}{\left[\frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}^2} - 1\right]^{1/n} \frac{d\zeta}{\zeta}} \quad (37)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}$ is the ratio of applied stress to the strength under rapid loading, and

$$\alpha = \beta \left[\frac{J(0)}{\hat{\sigma}}\right]^{1/n}$$

where

$$J(t) = \hat{J}t + J(0)$$

is the uniaxial creep function ($J(0)$ is the initial value of that function), \hat{J} and n are material constants, and β is a geometric factor, as suggested by Christensen and others [45], or by an equation such as (32). The number of cycles to failure, N , may be given by a damage

mechanics relationship such as Eqn. (15), or by a phenomenological relationship such as Eqn. (38)

$$N = \exp \left[2.3 \left[\frac{S/S_u - a}{b} \right] \right] 1/c \quad (38)$$

in which S is the stress amplitude, S_u is the ultimate strength under that type of loading, a , b , and c are assumed to be material constants. Hence, time dependent behavior such as viscoelastic deformation and creep deformation can enter the equation in that way.

SUMMARY

An attempt has been made to summarize typical approaches to the engineering subject of predicting the lifetime of materials and components. As a technical subdiscipline, at least the following issues are important to such a pursuit.

1. One must clearly define and thoroughly understand the mechanics and physics (chemistry, etc.) of the specific failure event to be predicted.
2. An appropriate geometric scale of the physical events to be modeled must be chosen such that details which are important to the failure process are included and those not important generalized so as to make the modeling process tractable.
3. Constitutive information must be introduced to characterize not only properties but the evolution of properties (or the damage that influences properties). This information must be soundly based on experimental observations and understandings.
4. A thorough analysis of the local state of stress must be compared with an accurate representation of the state of material using a correct philosophy dictated by pragmatism defined by the failure event.

We have also tried to suggest that some popular features of life prediction techniques are divagations. Perhaps the most blatant of these is the separation of cycle dependent and time dependent phenomena in laboratory investigations and analytical representations. This separation is a historical convenience which has practical utility in certain circumstances, but the "perspective of separation" is an obstacle to the continued development of life prediction methods. Likewise, "rules of thumb" which attempt to achieve phenomenological representations of life data (usually as empirical curve fitting) do not make appropriate use of the experimental information, the physical understanding, or the analytical modeling tools that can be applied to a more precise and detailed description of the physical events which actually determine the life of materials and components. However, these "divagations" play a major role in the practical life prediction methodologies which are popular at this writing. We must progress beyond this point if we are to design safe, reliable, and durable composite structures by intent rather than by chance.

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Figure 1. The concept of life as a criterion and a process that alters the state of stress and state of material.

Figure 2. Criteria which may be used to define life.

Figure 3. Types of physical behavior associated with the "process" which changes properties and behavior.

Figure 4. A general diagram of life as a function of the level of applied influence (load, temperature, etc.)

Figure 5. Types of damage initiation in composite materials.

Figure 6. Material element around the tip of a crack in an infinite medium, with a coordinate system typical for fracture mechanics discussions.

Figure 7. Illustration of local strain approach for an irregular load vs. time history. The notched member (a), having cyclic stress-strain and load-strain curves as in (b), is subjected to load history (c).

(d)

(e)

Figure 7. continued. The resulting load-strain response is shown in (d), and the local notch stress-strain response in (e). The strain ranges ($\Delta\epsilon$) and mean stresses (σ_0) for each closed stress-strain hysteresis loop are then used in predicting life.

Figure 8. Interlaminar normal stress near the intersection of cracks in adjacent plies.

Figure 9. Radiograph showing local delaminations between the 0° and 90° plies of a $[0/90_2]_s$ laminate near the point of intersection of matrix cracks in those plies.

Figure 10. Concept of representative volumes and critical elements.

Figure 11. Damage patterns (a) and the associated representative volume (b) for cross-ply laminated composite coupon.

Figure 12. Flow chart of the critical element concept.

$$F_r(\tau_1) = F_u - \int_0^{\tau_1/\tau_0} (F_u - F_e(\tau)) i \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_0}\right)^{i-1} d\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_0}\right)$$

Parameter
Generalized Time

τ_1/τ_0
 $(\frac{\tau}{\tau_0})^{i-1}$

Residual Strength Function
Initial Strength Function
Applied Strength Function
Critical Element Characterization

Figure 13. A generalized equation for the computation of residual strength.

Figure 14. A calculation of residual strength for successive block loading of a graphite epoxy laminate, and predicted life compared to observed data range.